

IMPACT OF A CERTAIN PRELIMINARY TRAINING PROGRAMME ON CRICKET PLAYERS' SPEED

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study was to investigate the effect of certain preliminary training programme on speed among cricket players. For the present study the 30 male cricket players from Puducherry were selected at random and their age ranged from 18 to 25 years. For the present study pre test - post test random group design which consists of control group and experimental group was used. The subjects were randomly assigned to two equal groups of fifteen each. Group 'A' underwent certain preliminary training programme only, group 'B' have not undergone any training. The data was collected before and after twelve weeks of training. The data was analyzed by applying Analysis of Co-Variance (ANCOVA). The level of significance was set at 0.05. It was observed that the twelve weeks of certain preliminary training have significantly improved the speed of cricket players.

Key Words: Certain Preliminary Training, Speed, Cricket Players.

Introduction:

Sports training is a programme of exercise designed to improve the skills and increase the energy capacities of an athlete for a particular event. Sports activities consist of motor movement and action and their success depends to a great extent on how correctly they are performed. Techniques of training and improvement of tactical efficiency play a vital role in a training process (Fox, 1984). Bompa (1999) suggested that the physiological goal of training is to improve body function and optimize athletic performance. Training is primarily a systematic athletic activity of long duration, which is progressively and individually graded. Human physiological functions are modeled to meet demanding tasks.

The concept of training is reflected in words or terms, which are given to separate components of training (technique training, strength training) or separate methods of procedures of doing physical exercise (interval training and circuit training). Training means are various physical exercises and their objects, methods and procedures, which are used for the improvement, maintenance and recovery of performance capacity and performance readiness. Certain preliminary training programme phase consists of the general preparation and specific preparation. Usually which can be subdivided into three different phases. One should always remember that this is a base creation phase with the objective to attain the previous training state, and the longest period of periodization must be devoted towards the preparatory period. The performance depends on preparatory period (Dick, 1997).

Periodization:

The roots of periodization come from Hans Selye's model, known as the General adaptation syndrome. The GAS describes three basic stages of response to stress: (a) the Alarm stage, involving the initial shock of the stimulus on the system, (b) the Resistance stage, involving the adaptation to the stimulus by the system, and (c) the Exhaustion stage, in that repairs are inadequate, and a decrease in system function results. The foundation of periodic training is keeping one's body in the resistance stage without ever going into the exhaustion stage. By adhering to cyclic training the body is given adequate time to recover from significant stress before additional training is undertaken. The response to a new stress is to first respond poorly and the response drops off. For example when the body is first exposed to sun a sunburn might develop. During the resistance stage adaptation improves the response to a higher level, called super compensation, than the previous equilibrium. The example would be that a suntan develops. The exhaustion stage is a continuation of the stimulus at too high a level and the increase gained from adaptation is now offset and all gains are lost. The example would be that wrinkles, spots, or even skin cancer develop. The goal in sports periodization is to reduce the stress at the point where the resistance stage ends so the body has time to recover. In this way the exhaustion stage does not reduce the gains achieved, the body can recover and remain above the original equilibrium point. The next cycle of increased stimulus now improves the response further and the equilibrium point continues to rise after each cycle.

Methodology:

The purpose of the study was to investigate the effect of certain preliminary training programme on speed among cricket players. For the present study the 30 male cricket players from Puducherry were selected at random and their age ranged from 18 to 21 years. For the present study pre test - post test random group design which consists of control group and experimental group was used. The subjects were randomly assigned to two equal groups of fifteen each. Group 'A' underwent certain preliminary training programme only, group 'B' have not

underwent any training. The data was collected before and after twelve weeks of training. The data was analyzed by applying Analysis of Co-Variance (ANCOVA). The level of significance was set at 0.05.

Results:

Table 1: Computation of Mean and Analysis of Covariance of Speed of Experimental and Control Groups

	Experimental Group	Control Group	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F
Pre Test Mean	7.33	7.39	BG	0.001	1	0.001	0.56
			WG	0.05	28	0.0017	
Post Test Mean	7.17	7.34	BG	0.38	1	0.38	133.00*
			WG	0.08	28	0.002	
Adjusted Post Mean	7.15	7.35	BG	0.39	1	0.39	150.42*
			WG	0.07	27	0.002	

* Significant at 0.05 level Table value for df 1 and 28 was 4.20, 1 and 27 was 4.21

The above table indicates the adjusted mean value of speed of experimental and control groups were 7.15 and 7.35 respectively. The obtained F-ratio of 140.42 for adjusted mean was greater than the table value 4.21 for the degrees of freedom 1 and 27 required for significance at 0.05 level of confidence. The result of the study indicates that there was a significant difference among experimental and control groups on speed. The above table also indicates that both pre and post test means of experimental and control groups differ significantly. The pre, post and adjusted post mean values of speed of both experimental and control groups are graphically represented in the figure 1.

Figure 1: Shows the Mean Values on Speed of Experimental Group and Control Groups

Conclusion:

It was observed that the twelve weeks of certain preliminary training group have significantly improved the speed of cricket players.

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